

USING GAMES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: The gamification of education can enhance levels of students' engagement similar to what games can do, to improve their particular skills and optimize their learning. This article goes into details about enjoyable experience of gamification in teaching, its main goals and benefits for learners. It aims to assess whether the use of gamification is likely to facilitate or undermine intrinsic motivation, and presents a summary of self-determination theory

Key words: Gamification, personality, programming environment, motivation, intrinsic motivation, self-determination theory, language.

Gamification can be a powerful tool in teaching English as a second language. By incorporating game elements into language learning activities, educators can make the learning process more interactive, engaging, and enjoyable for students. In the present study, educational games are considered as important teaching tools that have not received enough attention in EFL classes. If the teachers play more games in classes, their students' willingness to communicate will increase, which makes them more successful students. The main goals of gamification are to enhance certain abilities, introduce objectives that give learning a purpose, engage students, optimize learning, support behavior change, and socialize. In this study, we aimed to study whether the gamification affects students differently depending on their personality traits. More specifically, we aimed to investigate whether distinct components of gamification affect students' learning, their programming attitudes (trial and error behavior in the programming tasks submission for correction), and engagement depending on their personality traits (extroversion, openness, agreeableness, neuroticism, and conscientiousness) in the context of programming learning. Teachers believed that games amuse learners, help shy learners to participate, promote whole class participation, waste one's time, enable learners to acquire new experiences, and have more student-centered

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

classes. On the other hand, playing games does not increase anxiety. Gamification is sometimes defined as “a process of enhancing a service with (motivational) affordances for gameful experiences in order to support user's overall value creation”. This definition reflects the widely held belief that the goal of gamification is to influence user behavior through user motivation, and that this motivation in turn can be positively influenced by the motivational affordances commonly found in games. It is concluded that using games is an efficient way to teach English in the classroom. Following this method, you get the best results in the classroom. It increases students' motivation. Games prepare young learners for life, and they acquire positive social attitudes. Games teach sharing, helping each other, and working as a team. A child learns by doing, living, trying, and imitating. So this kind of learning is lasting. During games, some feelings, such as the pleasure of winning and the fear of losing, may arise. This gives the teacher an idea about the student's character. So, games are must-have activities for hardworking teachers.

The findings of the present study demonstrate that games are effective as energizers and educational tools that can provide enjoyment, pleasure, passionate involvement, structure, and motivation among other benefits; the researchers supported the trend towards using them as short warm-ups.

When learning exercises are held alongside games, instruction is assisted, and increases foreign languages students' achievement. Moreover, if English language is practiced with the help of games, the achievement of the learners can be higher than that from traditional education. According to Andrea (2011), games played a major role in achieving meaningful learning where the most productive and motivating learning experiences are taking place. This is a strong invitation for teachers to refer to games while teaching difficult tasks so as to maintain an interesting teaching environment. Games should be perceived as elements of the process of teaching, learners should benefit from games connected with English learning in the process of teaching-learning at the right time and the right place. When we consider the positive effects of language games, such as lowering learners' anxiety and providing meaningful use of a language in the classroom, this result is striking and should be investigated in detail. Since the perspectives of learners and teachers might vary, even about the specific issue such as learning English through games, teachers and researchers should conduct studies or action research to examine learners' views on several

FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

points to take into consideration when teaching a language and planning their lessons in a way that meets their individual learners' needs.

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FAN, TA'LIM, TEXNOLOGIYA VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI

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